

Cancel CCP's "Iron Curtain" in Hong Kong

Author: CPA Jim

(Picture source: AXIOS¹)

“Cancel Culture” is popular among some radical left Americans and Brits. They use cancel culture to destroy statues of Winston Churchill and George Washington. On 5 March 1946, Winston Churchill delivered “iron curtain” speech, in which he said “From Stettin in the Baltic to Trieste in the Adriatic, an iron curtain has descended across the continent” by USSR. On 5 March 2021, “Iron Curtain” descended in Hong Kong when Chinese Communist party (CCP) legislated Hong Kong election procedures in the USSR style with CCP characteristics, which was also mentioned by Lude Media.

What must be cancelled should be a great concern to respond to such “Iron Curtain”. It seems that CCP is very strong and nothing could be done to cancel CCP. In fact, CCP is very weak because if a person living in China just talks about holding a rally on the Tiananmen Square in Beijing to protest Great Firewall or government being unelected by

people at WeChat, that person will face troubles, such as being locked out of WeChat and being put into prison for threatening “national security” or “causing social disorder”.

There are at least two subtle points ordinary citizens could make a difference.

First, CCP fears the voices of Chinese people and it uses Great Firewall (GFW) to block voices of people resulting in many western media unable to be accessed by Chinese and Chinese unable to deliver truths about China at media platforms. GFW will unavoidably be extended to Hong Kong. Media censorship has been extended to Hong Kong, as reported by the Voice of America on 6 March 2021². Censorship under GFW, blocking voices of taxpayers suffering unfair treatment and heavy penalty by CCP tax authorities, citizens being inhumanely locked up at home in CCP virus pandemic, unfairly dismissed employees, deceived real estate consumers and independent accountants with the discoveries of accounting fraud or audit service tendering corruption, causes great loss to stakeholders. The maintenance of GFW is closely related to western big corporates. Readers to this article could find such western corporates by searching and analysing relevant media report, announcements and supplier or partnership information of both CCP entities and major western corporates. Take Twitter as an example. Twitter, operating censorship in the west to block voices of Chinese, supplied advertisement services to Huawei, a CCP military entity operating GFW and developing surveillances technology used for genocide in Xinjiang. As reported by media and according to non-executive director compensation system disclosed in its 2019 annual report, Twitter hired Feifei Li, associated with the United Front of CCP, with compensation both in cash and restricted stock units as non-executive director.³

Second, CCP gets financed from the west to operate GFW, enforce National Security Law in Hong Kong and cause disorder in South China

Sea. Many big west corporates and wealth management products have investments in such financings. Readers to this article could find such western corporates by searching and analysing relevant announcements and liabilities information of CCP entities and investments information of major western corporates including financial institutions, such as HSBC. HSBC had direct investments in CCP regimes, as disclosed on page 140 of its annual report as at 31 Dec 2020, even after enforcing National Security Law. HSBC had also persuaded UK MPs into keeping Huawei 5G equipment, referring to CCP's threat of punishment,⁴ and froze Hong Kong pro-democracy citizens' accounts illegally.

But HSBC had taken many deposits in Europe, North American and Asia, and issued bonds in the US, shares in the UK and the US, which could also be verified on page 86 and frontpage of the 2020 annual report of HSBC, respectively.

In-country foreign currency and cross-border amounts outstanding

		Banks	Government and official institutions	Other	Total
	Footnotes	\$bn	\$bn	\$bn	\$bn
At 31 Dec 2020					
US		5.4	65.4	53.1	123.9
UK		15.9	10.8	45.1	71.8
Mainland China		21.7	14.0	35.4	71.1
Hong Kong		4.1	0.3	54.9	59.3
Japan		14.4	31.7	6.2	52.3
Germany		17.4	12.4	7.6	37.4
Canada		11.8	13.0	5.9	30.7
France	1	9.6	10.8	7.9	28.3
Singapore	1	1.6	11.0	14.8	27.4

Title of each class	Trading Symbol(s)	Name of each exchange on which registered
Ordinary Shares, nominal value US\$0.50 each (GB0005405286)	HSBA 5	London Stock Exchange Hong Kong Stock Exchange
	HSBC.BH	Bermuda Stock Exchange
	HSBC	New York Stock Exchange
American Depository Shares, each representing 5 Ordinary Shares of nominal value US\$0.50 each (US4042804066)	HSBC	New York Stock Exchange

<u>7.625% Subordinated Notes due 2032 (US404280AF65)</u>	<u>HSBC/32A</u>	<u>New York Stock Exchange</u>
<u>7.35% Subordinated Notes due 2032 (US404280AE90)</u>	<u>HSBC/32B</u>	<u>New York Stock Exchange</u>
<u>6.5% Subordinated Notes 2036 (US404280AG49)</u>	<u>HSBC36</u>	<u>New York Stock Exchange</u>
<u>6.5% Subordinated Notes 2037 (US404280AH22)</u>	<u>HSBC37</u>	<u>New York Stock Exchange</u>
<u>6.8% Subordinated Notes Due 2038 (US404280AJ87)</u>	<u>HSBC38</u>	<u>New York Stock Exchange</u>
<u>5.10% Senior Unsecured Notes Due 2021 (US404280AK50)</u>	<u>HSBC21</u>	<u>New York Stock Exchange</u>
<u>4.875% Senior Unsecured Notes Due 2022 (US404280AL34)</u>	<u>HSBC22</u>	<u>New York Stock Exchange</u>
<u>6.100% Senior Unsecured Notes due 2042 (US404280AM17)</u>	<u>HSBC42</u>	<u>New York Stock Exchange</u>
<u>4.00% Senior Unsecured Notes Due 2022 (US404280AN99)</u>	<u>HSBC22A</u>	<u>New York Stock Exchange</u>

(Picture source: [SEC⁵](#))

Those operating GFW or investing CCP financial investments, either directly or indirectly such as through investing financial instruments of HSBC, should be cancelled by divesting bonds, withdrawing deposits, transferring fund, redeeming shares in the wealth management products, terminating business relation, etc to fight back CCP's deprivation of Hong Kong Autonomy, CCP virus biowarfare coverup and genocide in Xinjiang.

References:

- 1 Iron Curtain descends on Hong Kong. <https://www.axios.com/china-hong-kong-national-security-law-51833a86-9a54-4cdc-9234-0bdd4db2b369.html>
- 2 Media censorship. <https://www.voanews.com/press-freedom/chinas-media-repression-extends-hong-kong-report-finds>
- 3 Who is funding Twitter censorship? <https://gnews.org/508102/>
- 4.Huawei and CCP. <https://www.ans.org/news/article-267/us-offers-support-for-uk-new-nuclear-build/>.
- 5.2020 HSBC annual report. <https://www.sec.gov/ix?doc=/Archives/edgar/data/1089113/000162828021003046/hsbc-20201231.htm>

(The above content only represents the author's personal opinion)